

Applicability of Hammett Equation in the Iodination of Acetophenones

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The rate constants for the iodination of acetophenones have been measured colorimetrically in 1.388(*M*) aqueous perchloric acid. The value of ρ , the reaction constant and the resonance interaction energy for the para substituents have also been calculated. A probable transition state consistent with the experimental results has been proposed and evidences are furnished in support of the proposed transition state.

In the present work the iodination of acetophenones was carried out colorimetrically using 1.388(*M*) aqueous perchloric acid as the solvent. The applicability of the Hammett equation¹ has been tested. From the slope of the regression line fitted to $\log k$ and σ_0^2 for *m*-substituted compounds, the value of ρ , the reaction constant, has been calculated at various temperatures. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and resonance interaction energy ($\Delta\Delta F$) relating to various substituents have been determined. The resonance interaction energy differences in going from reactant to transition state have been evaluated by using the free energy term³, $-2.303RT \rho(\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0)$. The data throw considerable light on the electron distribution in the transition state.

EXPERIMENTAL

The acetophenone solution was contained in a glass cell through which the colorimeter plunger can move up and down freely. The glass cell is enclosed in another jacket through which water is circulated from a large thermostat with the help of a circulating pump to maintain constant temperature in the reaction cell. The cell and the jacket can be moved up and down by means of an adjusting arrangement. They are also removable for cleaning.

At the lowest adjustment, the system of cell and jacket stands directly on a solid platform in the colorimeter. With this arrangement on one side the colorimeter is provided on the other side with a cup-plunger system for maintaining a constant depth of absorbing layer with variable contributions from the colorimetric standard solution of methyl orange in water. The fields were viewed through a dense blue filter applied to the usual incandescent bulb which supplies a deep blue-violet light representing a fairly narrow spectral band. The filters are placed immediately over the ends of the plunger.

1. L. P. Hammett, "Physical Organic Chemistry", McGraw Hill., New York, 1940, p. 193.
2. W. R. Taft (Jr.), *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1805.
3. Van Bekkum, H. Verkade P.E. and Wepster, B.M. *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1959, **78**, 815.

Method of Measurement : Because of the great instability in an open cup of aqueous iodine solution containing no iodide ion an artificial colorimetric standard of dilute (4 mg. per litre) solution of methyl orange in water was used. Although this solution differs markedly in colour from iodine solutions in general illumination, when viewed by the light transmitted by the filter, methyl orange and iodine solutions are indistinguishable by eye over the range of concentrations used.

The reaction mixture consisting of 10 ml. of the 0.02(*M*) solution of the ketone in 1.388 (*M*) perchloric Acid and 1 ml. of 0.01 (*M*) solution of aqueous potassium iodide was taken in the reaction cell of the colorimeter. The water was circulated from a large thermostat through the jacketed tube of the cell for at least 30 minutes to enable the solution to attain the temperature of the bath. The reaction was then started by adding a small crystal of the oxidising agent, solid sodium nitrate, and readings were taken. Time was measured from the instant of addition of oxidising agent and this procedure allows a very satisfactory approximation to instantaneous mixing, since the ketone concentration, upon which alone the rate depends, is at its correct initial value even before mixing.

Rate calculation : The reaction is first-order in ketone and independent of iodine concentration. The specific reaction rate was calculated by using the following rate equation suggested by Hammett *et al.*⁴

$$h = h_0 - \frac{kC_{KH}^0 \cdot t}{m \cdot f}$$

where *k* is the specific reaction rate,

C_{KH}^0 is the initial concentration of the ketone,

'*m*' and '*f*' are the constants.

The value of *f* = 2 if sodium nitrate is used as the oxidising agent, and 2.5 if sodium iodate is used as the oxidising agent.

The plot of '*h*' against '*t*' (time) gave in all cases a straight line whose slope is equal to $\frac{-kC_{KH}^0}{m \cdot f}$, from which the value of '*k*' was calculated. The specific reaction rates for various acetophenones at 30° are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Name of the substituent in acetophenone	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -F	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃
$k_{30} \times 10^4 \text{ Sec.}^{-1}$	42.00	37.00	40.12	39.91	49.36	51.00	34.69	39.82	53.80

DISCUSSION

The acid catalysed reaction of acetophenone and substituted acetophenones with iodine in the presence of excess of perchloric acid is a unimolecular substitution reaction.

4. L. Zuckar and L. P. Hammett. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2779.

The acid catalysed prototropic change of the compound CH_3COR may be represented as follows⁵:—

The first step of the process is the co-ordination of the catalyst with the ketone. The co-ordination is a relatively rapid process but the second step is considerably slower and is, therefore, the rate-determining step. The prototropic change depends upon the overall enolisation which, on the other hand, depends upon the stability of the carbonium ion intermediate (A). Any substituent which facilitates the carbonium ion facilitates the reaction also. The electron donating substituents in R will stabilise the carbonium ion and enhance the reaction rate, whereas electron attracting substituents will destabilise the intermediate and retard the reaction rate.

Our results confirm that the reaction is facilitated by electron-donating groups such as methyl, methoxy etc. and retarded by electron attracting groups such as nitro, chloro etc. and the order of velocity of reaction is :

Applicability of Hammett Equation : A regression line was fitted to the $\log k$ against σ_p ². The specific reaction rate for meta substituted compounds at three different temperatures are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Name of the substituent in acetophenone	Values of $k \times 10^4$ in sec. ⁻¹		
	30°	35°	40°
<i>m</i> -methyl	53.80	71.31	92.90
<i>m</i> -chloro	39.82	56.10	81.60
Un-substituted	42.00	60.01	88.00
<i>m</i> -nitro	34.69	47.99	68.57

The reaction constant (ρ), correlation coefficient (r) and the intercept with the ordinate ($\log k_0$) are given in Table 3.

5. S. W. Benson, "The Foundations of Chemical Kinetics", 1960, p. 572.

TABLE 3

Values of ρ , r and $\log k_0$

Temp. in °C	ρ	r	$-\log k_0$
30	-1.785	0.983	1.623
35	-1.66	0.986	1.80
40	-1.428	0.945	1.945

The absolute value of ' ρ ' decreases with rise of temperature showing that the reaction series is isocentropic⁶. As is expected the negative sign of ' ρ ' indicates that the reaction is aided by electron donation to the seat of reaction.

Effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\log k - \log k_0}{\rho}$) and resonance energy difference³ ($\Delta\Delta F_p = -2.303RT\rho(\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0)$) are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4

Effective sigma values and resonance energy difference

Substituent on acetophenone	p -OCH ₃	p -CH ₃	p -Cl	p -NO ₂
$\bar{\sigma}$	-0.1260	-0.1226	+0.0091	+0.112
$\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0$	-0.006	+0.0274	-0.2609	-0.708]
$\Delta\Delta F_p$ in K.Cal/mole.	-0.01236	+0.05641	-0.5370	-1.456]

It is evident from the above results that the effective sigma values for the ketone series differs from σ_0 only in the case of the p -nitro and p -chloro phenyl group.

The results given above imply that a positively charged transition state is stabilised by resonance interaction with the electron withdrawing nitro group and this is quite striking. This is, however, consistent with the structure of the transition state in which one of the hydrogen atoms from the methyl group adjacent to the $>C=O$ group is removed as a proton. The transition state for the acid catalysed enolisation will be intermediate between ketone conjugate acid and enol. Therefore, the carbonyl carbon atom will be electron deficient and positive. The following transition state may be proposed for the acid catalysed iodination of acetophenone.

On the basis of the above transition state the interaction of the nitro group with the developing enoldouble bond may be represented as below :

Support for this transition state can be found on resolution of the overall enolisation into two consecutive steps: (i) equilibrium protonation of the ketone carbonyl group and (ii) deprotonation at alpha-carbon of the conjugated acid. If step (ii) is assumed to be rate determining then obviously, the deprotonation reaction at alpha-carbon of conjugate acid would involve a transition state as represented by I.

If k_2 is the rate of deprotonation (at alpha-carbon atom) of the conjugate acid for which k_1 is the acid dissociation constant and k is the measured rate of enolisation, then

$$k_2 = k_1 \cdot k \text{ and hence } \rho_2 = \rho_1 + \rho$$

A regression line was fitted to $\log k_1$ values⁷ and σ_0 data for the meta-substituted compounds. The derived figures are $\rho_1 = +2.17$, intercept of the regression line with the ordinate ($\log k_0 = -6.15$) and $\rho_2 = 2.17 - 1.795 = +0.375^*$. Relative value of k_2 for the ketones were derived from the measured values of enolisation and calculated values of dissociation constants. The effective sigma values and resonance interaction energy differences for the deprotonation reaction at alpha-carbon of conjugate acid for the para substituents are listed in Table 5.

7. R. Stewart and K. Yates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 6355.

* ρ value at 25° is -1.795 .

TABLE 5

Effective sigma values and resonance energy difference

Substituent on acetophenone	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -F	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃
$\bar{\sigma}$	-3.18	-1.414	-0.853	+0.840	+0.7467
$\bar{\sigma}-\sigma_0$	-3.98	-1.68	-1.02	+0.99	+0.866
$\Delta\Delta F_p$ in K.Cal/mole	+2.048	+0.865	+0.525	-0.505	-0.446

In the transition state the bond between the methylene group and the protonated carbonyl group develops enol double bond character and hence because of its resultant conjugation with the methoxy group the resonance interaction of the methoxy group is enhanced in the manner shown below :

This increased resonance is possible only in the transition state but not in the conjugate acid where the bond in question cannot assume double bond character. The magnitude and the negative sign of the resonance interaction energy values are consistent with the enhanced para interaction energy in the transition state.

The positive sign of the resonance interaction energy for the para nitro group indicates a decrease in para interaction energy which may be explained as follows :

A negative charge on the methylene carbon atom is absolutely essential for development of the enol double bond and hence in the formation and stability of the transition state. The electron withdrawing nitro group decreases the electron density from the methylene carbon atom by withdrawing electron from the developing enol double bond in the transition state. On the other hand, the electron density of the methylene carbon atom in the conjugate acid is not affected due to the absence of the developing enol double bond. This explains why the significance of the resonance interaction of the nitro group is reduced in the transition state as compared to that in the conjugate acid.

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